

Bio-inspired mix design optimization of self-compacting concrete using machine learning algorithms

ABSTRACT: Concrete is an indispensable material for construction activities. Determining optimal concrete-mix proportions is an essential and complicated task. This paper focusses on using hybrid bio-inspired optimization algorithms by combining differential evolution (DE) and cuckoo search (CS) namely, Differential Cuckoo Search for optimizing concrete mix proportions. It also involves choosing the best among the different strength prediction machine learning models i.e., Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) and Support Vector Machine Regression (SVR). The efficiency of the hybrid bio-inspired algorithms is compared with the popular CS and DE using eleven benchmark test functions. Among them, the best one has been chosen to solve a mix design optimization problem to maximize compressive strength, to minimize carbon emissions and to minimize cost. It is observed from the results that ANN achieved a 30% increased compressive strength in comparison with SVR based framework. For minimization of cost as well as minimization of embodied carbon scenarios, both the machine learning models were able to produce optimal mix proportions with a very small variation. The results obtained show the efficiency of the hybrid algorithm in combination with the prediction model to achieve the optimal mix proportions for different scenarios.

Keywords: Bio-Inspired Algorithms, Swarm Intelligence Algorithms, Machine Learning, Prediction model, Concrete Mix Design, Cuckoo Search, Differential Evolution.

1 Introduction

Mix-design of concrete is to obtain appropriate weight proportions of various concrete constituents for attaining the desired strength. There are many empirical methods and standard ratios for finding mix proportions of normal concrete in various standard codes. With the development in the construction industry, the demand for properties of concrete like high strength, high workability, sustainability, etc., has increased. For satisfying different desired properties new kinds of concrete like Self Compacting Concrete (SCC), High-Performance Concrete (HPC), Ultra High-Performance Concrete (UHPC) are developed incorporating mineral and chemical admixtures (Newman & Choo, 2003). These mineral admixtures or supplementary cementitious materials help in not only reducing cost and eco-index but even enhance few mechanical properties of concrete. Among all the newly developed concretes, SCC is gaining attention and is practically used by many contractors across India. The main problem with SCC is its mix design; unlike normal concrete, SCC has many constituents in its mix design. Varying each parameter in the mix design has shown significant changes with respect to the compressive strength of the mix. There are no Indian standards for preparation of SCC and to obtain the optimal mix design for three different scenarios, a Machine Learning-based optimization approach is proposed in this manuscript. The three scenarios considered in this work are as follows: first, research work in the field of construction materials is focused on diverse objectives. There are several research-works that present various approaches to design optimal concrete mix proportions, thereby attempt to improve the compressive strength. Second, in the real world, the contractor needs to come up with a low-cost product without compromising the compressive strength as well as durability. Hence an economical mix design is essential. Finally, in recent times as the world is focusing on reducing carbon emissions and is showing interest in the use of green materials. Based on these three scenarios, the contribution of this proposed research work is outlined into three objectives. The first objective is to maximize compressive strength; second is to minimize the cost of the optimal mix design and the third objective is to obtain an eco-friendly

mix design without compromising on compressive strength. The accuracy of the resultant mix proportions is highly dependent on the accuracy of the strength prediction model. Several attempts have been made by various researchers in the past to develop strength prediction models of concrete using various machine learning algorithms. Gupta et al. (2007) used support vector machine to accurately predict the compressive strengths of normal concrete. Zain & Abd (2009) used multiple non-linear regression model to predict compressive strengths of HPC. Few research works have used tree-based machine learning models and Neural Networks to predict compressive strengths of HPC. (Deepa, Sathya & Prem, 2010; Huang, Paolo & Stephan 2011). Duta et al. (2018) and Chopra et al. (2018) have compared the performance of various machine learning techniques to accurately predict the compressive strengths of normal concrete.

Yeh (1999) used neural network and linear programming approaches to optimize the proportions of the concrete mix to enhance workability and compressive strength. Cheng et al. (2014) have developed a novel Genetic Algorithm based Evolutionary Support Vector Machine for Optimizing High-Performance Concrete Mixture. Similarly, Lee & Yoon (2009) proposed a modified harmony search algorithm and neural networks for concrete mix proportion design, Reddy et al. (1993) proposed expert system for optimum design of concrete structures, Pham et al. (2016) predicted the compressive strength of high-performance concrete using metaheuristic-optimized least squares support vector regression and Chou et al. (2011) optimized the prediction accuracy of concrete compressive strength based on a comparison of data-mining techniques. Naseri et al (2020), developed a methodology to generate sustainable mix proportions for concretes with strengths of 20-70 MPa. Azimi et al. (2020), developed linear and non-linear SVM models for prediction of fresh and hardened properties of high volume fly ash concrete. This research work attempts to compare two different machine learning models and then use them to obtain optimal mix proportions. The data for this research work is a compilation of past published

research works and databases, and all the features (independent variables) are of the continuous (numeric) data type. The proposed work focusses on comparison of two different prediction models, namely Support Vector Machine (SVM), Artificial Neural Network (ANN) and these models are combined with the optimization algorithm to obtain mix proportions.

The novelty of the approach lies in the hybrid optimization approach and also the entire framework used for designing optimal concrete mix. For optimization, hybrid algorithms are proposed which are a hybrid between Cuckoo search and Differential Evolution. These new algorithms are compared with its parent algorithms DE and CS using eleven mathematical test functions. The most robust hybrid optimization algorithm is used to predict the optimal mix proportion under all the three scenarios (i.e., (i) finding the mix proportion which provides the maximum compressive strength; (ii) mix proportion which is the most economical for a desired compressive strength and (iii) mix proportion which is has least embodied carbon for a desired compressive strength).

The proposed framework can be explained into two modules where the first module is a machine learning module and the other is optimization module which is schematically presented in Figure 1.

Module -1: Machine Learning module

In this module, two types of machine learning models namely, Artificial Neural Network and Support Vector Machine are trained and tested with the existing mix proportions and corresponding 28-day compressive strength data collected from past research works and databases. From this training and validation, the knowledge models are obtained and is used in the following optimization module.

Figure 1 – The Proposed framework for mix design optimization.

Module – 2: Optimization module

In this module, there are two stages: Choice of Algorithm, and ML based Optimization.

Stage-1: Choosing the robust bio-inspired optimization algorithm

In this stage, two hybrid bio-inspired optimization algorithms namely differential cuckoo search 1 and 2 are compared with cuckoo search, differential evolution and modified cuckoo search algorithms. For comparison of the algorithms, eleven benchmark mathematical test functions are used. The shapes and landscapes of the test functions, and a description about each function are presented in Table 5 and Table 6 respectively. Based on the comparison of performance metrics over the test functions, a robust algorithm is chosen.

Stage-2: Machine learning based optimization to obtain optimal mix proportions

In this stage, the robust optimization algorithm obtained from stage -1 is used to search the optimal mix proportion for all the three scenarios with the help of the knowledge models obtained from machine learning module.

Scenario-1: In this scenario, the objective is to maximize compressive strength, for this, the robust bio-inspired optimization algorithm is used to search the quantities of each component of SCC mix within its specified boundaries such that they satisfy the constraints of the EFNARC (2002) guidelines (EFNARC 1999; EFNARC 2002; Group, 2005). Every mix proportion generated in every iteration is fed into the knowledge model to obtain their corresponding predicted compressive strength. This process terminates until the algorithm converges to maximum compressive strength.

Scenario-2: The objective in this scenario is to obtain the economical (minimize the cost) mix proportion which produces desired compressive strength. Similar to scenario-1, the robust bio-inspired optimization

algorithm searches within its search space and satisfy the constraints. In addition to the EFNARC constraints, the compressive strength constraint is also added in this scenario. The compressive strength in every iteration is obtained from the knowledge models similar to the scenario-1. The algorithm search terminates when it converges to a mix proportion which has the least cost and its compressive strength is more than the desired compressive strength.

Scenario -3: In this scenario, the objective is to minimize the embodied carbon or obtain the most eco-friendly mix proportion. The working mechanism is the same as that of scenario-2, instead of targeting a least-cost mix proportion, we target a mix proportion with least embodied carbon. At the end of the whole process, we can obtain an optimal mix proportion for any of the three scenarios.

2 Machine Learning module

2.1 Data Set Description:

The strength and accuracy of any machine learning model are dependent on the comprehensiveness of the database or learning data. The dataset for the current study consists of 708 records which were collected from several reputed research works. The data set contains mix proportions and their 28-day compressive strength values. The materials involved are Fly ash, GGBS, Cement, Coarse Aggregate, Fine aggregate, Superplasticizer and Water. The statics of these materials in the database is shown in the Table 1. As there are 7 independent variables (mix proportions) and 1 dependent variable, a feature selection technique is used to identify the most effecting variable (feature) form the seven independent variables; Entropy-based information gain technique is used to assign weights to each independent variable. The weights obtained are listed in Table 2. Based on this feature selection method, we can see that the contribution of superplasticizer and coarse aggregate is negligible compared to other mix constituents. The complete data set is split into training and testing in a ratio of 70:30, and the two models are trained and tested with this data.

Table 1 Data Statistics

Material (kg/m ³)	Max	Min	Mean	Variance
Cement	540	102	261.693	11238.970
Blast Furnace Slag	359.4	0	92.679	7303.041
Fly Ash	200.1	0	68.206	4444.715
Coarse Aggregate	1145	801	944.486	6701.340
Water	247	121.75	182.790	374.588
Superplasticizer	32.2	0	7.859	26.878
Fine Aggregate	992.6	594	763.278	5398.075
Concrete Compressive Strength (MPa)	81.751	8.535	37.239	226.223

Table 2 Information Gain (Weights) of Variables

Variable Name	Weight
Cement (C)	0.3396
Blast Furnace Slag (G)	0.2358
Fly Ash (F)	0.1157
Fine Aggregate (FA)	0.1202
Coarse Aggregate (CA)	0.0479
Water (W)	0.1757
Super plasticizer (SP)	0.0580

2.2 Artificial Neural Network

Neural networks are machine learning models which are used to establish a relationship between variables whose connection is unknown or very complex. Neural networks are a mimic of the functioning of the brain; they consist of an input layer, an output layer, and at least one hidden layer. The input layer is the layer which gets signals from the environment and the output layer is the one that comprehends those responses. Hidden layers are the non-linear computational members where the actual processing happens. Due to the complex relationship between mix proportions and compressive strength, these neural network models are used to predict compressive strength by taking the mix proportions as inputs in this article. Many researchers in the past have used a similar approach to predict the compressive strength of various types of concrete (Storn & Price, 1997; Yang, 2014). For the current problem, each component used in the mixture is taken as a separate neuron, therefore the input layer comprises of 7 neurons and a single hidden layer is assumed and the number of hidden nodes is taken to be five after

various trials. The network architecture is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Neural Network Architecture

2.3 Support Vector Machine

The Support Vector Algorithm (SV) was developed in the 1960s for learning models using training data to generalize well on testing data. It was based on statistical learning theory. The Support Vector Machine which was developed in the mid 1990s, is commonly used for classification tasks. SV learning approach was then applied to temporal data predictions and also regression problems too. Given an n-dimensional space of input patterns, the goal of the induction algorithm used for training the SVM is to minimize the deviation from the actually observed target values. A threshold (epsilon) specifies the level of tolerable deviation between the actual output and the predicted output. Rather than fitting a linear hyperplane and evaluating errors on the position of the points on either side of the plane, the Support Vector Regression model evaluates the mean square error from the predicted point and the closest point on the hyper plane.

This model of error is more appropriate for least-squares data fitting, which ensures that the SVM can be used for regression. The other mechanisms, such as the use of kernel functions to map non-linear data to a higher dimension (kernel trick) remains the same for SVM based classification and regression models. A Linear Support Vector Regression (Linear SVR) model considers only linear kernels, whereas the SVR model in our work considers the Radial Basis Function for Computing the kernel matrix. The epsilon value is set to default of 0.1.

2.4 Model Evaluation

2.4.1 Pearson correlation coefficient (R)

The Pearson correlation coefficient is a statistical measure used to calculate the strength between two sets of parameters. R ranges from -1 to 1. The efficiency of the model in predicting the output can be obtained through the analysis of R values. The Pearson correlation coefficient measures the extent of deviation of the observed value from the best-fit line. It is defined as:

$$R = \frac{n(\sum_{i=1}^n O_i - P_i) - (\sum_{i=1}^n O_i) \cdot (\sum_{i=1}^n P_i)}{\sqrt{[n \sum_{i=1}^n O_i^2 - (\sum_{i=1}^n O_i)^2] \cdot [n \sum_{i=1}^n P_i^2 - (\sum_{i=1}^n P_i)^2]}} \quad (1)$$

2.4.2 Coefficient of determination (R^2)

Coefficient of determination is the square of Pearson correlation coefficient. It gives the variance between the predicted and the observed values. It gives a measure of the ability of the regression line to predict the data. R^2 is calculated as:

$$R^2 = \frac{[\sum_{i=1}^n (O_i - \bar{O}_i) \cdot (P_i - \bar{P}_i)]^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n (O_i - \bar{O}_i) \cdot \sum_{i=1}^n (P_i - \bar{P}_i)} \quad (2)$$

2.4.3 Mean absolute error (MAE)

Mean absolute error is the error calculated between two continues variables of the same parameter; in

the present study, it refers to compressive strength. MAE is equal to the average distance between the y = x line (identity line) and the point in the scatter plot of (x, y), where x and y are observed and predicted values of compressive strength. The formula for MAE is:

$$MAE = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n |O_i - P_i|}{n} \quad (3)$$

2.4.4 Root mean square error (RMSE)

Root mean square deviation or error is the measure of the standard deviation of prediction errors (residuals). It represents the degree of concentration of data points around the best-fit line. RMSE is evaluated using the following expression:

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (P_i - O_i)^2}{n}} \quad (5)$$

2.4.5 Mean absolute percentage error (MAPE)

Mean absolute percentage error evaluates the accuracy of a predicted model in terms of percentage.

MAPE is expressed as follows:

$$MAPE = \frac{100\%}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \left| \frac{O_i - P_i}{O_i} \right| \quad (6)$$

in which O_i , P_i represents the observed and predicted values, while n represents the number of test data.

Using the above-mentioned formulae for the evaluation metric and the output from different ML techniques viz., observed and predicted values, the efficiency of the ML technique is analyzed and the results are discussed in the following section.

3 Optimization module

3.1 Differential Cuckoo Search algorithm (DCS)

Differential Cuckoo Search Algorithm is a proposed bio-inspired hybrid algorithm combining both cuckoo search as well as differential evolution. It has shown a better convergence and robustness compared to its parent algorithms. To completely understand this new hybrid algorithm, one should know about both cuckoo search as well as Differential Evolution.

3.1.1 Differential Evolution (DE)

Differential Evolution, as the name, signifies it is an evolutionary based algorithm developed by Storn and Price (1997) . It is a vector based algorithm having similarities with Genetic Algorithm (GA) and Pattern Search (PS). In many ways, DE is much better than GA and can also be called as an upgrade to GA. One of the major advantages is, it uses both updating equations and also updates using vectors. This nullifies the computational costs incurred in encoding and decoding as in GA. This also makes the user implement it easily and even work on its various modifications.

Algorithm

Consider an objective function containing variables; assume an initial population as n.

$$x_i^{cur} = (x_{i,1}^{cur}, x_{i,2}^{cur}, x_{i,3}^{cur}, \dots, x_{i,t=d}^{cur}) \quad (7)$$

In Eq. 1, *cur* means a current solution, 'i' can take values from 1 to n corresponding to each population and d is the number of variables of objective function f(x). As this is an evolutionary-based algorithm, this is considered to be a chromosome. There are three main steps in DE, (i) mutation, (ii) crossover, and (iii) selection.

$$\text{Mutation: } v_i^{updt} = x_i^{cur} + F * (x_j^{cur} - x_k^{cur}) \quad (8)$$

Here updt means updated chromosome, $i, j, k \in [1, n]$ and j, k are randomly chosen $F \in [0, 2]$ is a mutation parameter.

$$\text{Crossover } u_{i,t}^{updt} = \begin{cases} v_{i,t}^{updt} & \text{if } r_i \leq C \\ x_{i,t}^{cur} & \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

Here C is the crossover parameter and r_i is a random number generated for i^{th} population and $t \in [1, d]$ and this operation is done for every chromosome.

$$\text{Selection } x_i^{new} = \begin{cases} u_i^{updt} & \text{if } f(u_i^{updt}) \leq f(x_i^{cur}) \\ x_i^{cur} & \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

In this process, the new population is generated and is selected between the current and updated population based on their objective function value. The whole DE algorithm is based on two parameters F and C . By varying these the exploration and exploitation of the search mechanism can be controlled.

3.1.2 Cuckoo search algorithm

Cuckoo Search (CS) is a Swarm Intelligence (SI) based, bio-inspired optimization algorithm. Swarm Intelligence is a collective intelligence of self-adaptive systems. We can see most of this kind of behaviour in nature for survival by many species. Cuckoo search is based on one such behaviour of cuckoo birds in their breeding methods (Gandomi et al., 2013). Compared to many other swarm intelligence algorithms, the Cuckoo search uses levy flights instead of conventional random walk. This makes its search much better than many SI based optimization algorithms.

Algorithm

Assume an objective function containing ' d ' variables (dimensions) and a number ' n ' nests. Here, instead of the population, we use nests as the algorithm is based on the breeding pattern of cuckoo birds.

$$x_i^{cur} = (x_{i,1}^{cur}, x_{i,2}^{cur}, x_{i,3}^{cur}, \dots, x_{i,t=d}^{cur}) \quad (11)$$

Here cur means current solution, i can take values from 1 to n corresponding to each population and d is the number of variables of objective function $f(x)$. In cuckoo search, the searching happens in two mechanisms (i) global search and (ii) local search (Yang & Deb, 2009). The shift is controlled by a switching parameter P_a . The global search happens using a special random walk called levy flight. Levy flight is a random number generator which uses levy distribution (Checkkin et al., 2008). One of the popular methods to generate random numbers using levy distribution is using Magenta Algorithm.

$$step = \frac{u}{|v|^{\frac{1}{\beta}}} \quad (12)$$

Here, s is the step length and u and v are drawn from the normal distribution. $u \sim N(0, \sigma u^2)$ and $v \sim N(0, \sigma v^2)$.

$$\sigma u = \begin{cases} \Gamma(1 + \beta) * \sin(\pi * \frac{\beta}{2}) \\ \Gamma[\frac{1 + \beta}{2}] * \beta * 2^{\frac{\beta-1}{2}} \end{cases}^{1/\beta}, \sigma v = 1 \quad (13)$$

The new solution is updated using this same magenta algorithm.

$$x_i^{new} = x_i^{cur} + \alpha * L(step, \beta) \quad (14)$$

The local search is done by conventional random walk

$$x_i^{new} = x_i^{cur} + \alpha * (x_j^{cur} - x_k^{cur}) \quad (15)$$

Here, $i, j, k \in [1, n]$ and are chosen randomly.

The main advantage of CS is its searching mechanism which almost mimics the natural phenomenon. This advantage is obtained due to levy-flight based search steps. Taking this levy-flight based random search steps and combining them with the search mechanism of DE, the rate of convergence and robustness of the algorithm is improved. Two versions of hybridization, namely, differential cuckoo search-type 1, and type 2 are compared in this manuscript.

3.1.3 *Differential Cuckoo Search*

The hybrid algorithm is a combination of both differential evolution and cuckoo search. This algorithm takes the advantages of both the parent algorithms to enhance the convergence rate without compromising on the robustness. The main advantage of CS is its searching mechanism which mimics the natural phenomenon. This is obtained due to levy-flight based search steps. Hence this study uses a Hybrid Algorithm that includes Differential Evolution's Diverse search mechanism along with CS search mechanism. Table 4 shows the modifications of all the hybrid algorithms considered for this study.

3.2 *Mix Design Optimization*

3.2.1 *Scenario 1:*

As mentioned earlier, every researcher wants to enhance the compressive strength of concrete. For finding out the optimal mix proportion which produces maximum compressive strength, he/she has to prepare various samples with varying mix proportions and test for 28 days and finalizing the mix which corresponds to highest strength to be the best mix. But there is a fundamental assumption, that is the highest compressive strength mix proportion is within the proportions taken for study. This may or may not be true all the time. To overcome this situation and nullify the work involved in casting, curing and testing, the proposed method can be incorporated. By using the ML models from Section 3 we can develop compressive strength prediction models. These ML models can be used along with the best optimization algorithm obtained from section 2 to achieve the best mix proportions, which will maximize the compressive strength of concrete. The mathematical model for the same is as follows:

Objective function: Maximize compressive strength (output from developed ML models)

Constraints: The mix proportions should follow EFNARC guidelines.

$$380 < \text{Cement} + \text{Flyash} + \text{Ground Grannular Blastfurnace Slag} < 600$$

$$150 < \textit{Water} < 210$$

$$750 < \textit{Coarse Aggregate} < 1000$$

$$0.48 * \textit{Total Aggregate} < \textit{Fine Aggregate} < 0.55 * \textit{Total Aggregate}$$

**All the constraints are defined by the mass of material for making 1 m³ of concrete
convergence percentage = (Number of populations converged)/ (total number of population = 50)
*100.

Each optimization algorithm is run for 60 times, each time for 100 iterations using 50 population. The minimum, maximum and standard deviation for minimum function value is also reported similarly. Let us consider that we are trying to optimize an optimization function where the global optima are zero. After 100 iterations with 50 population, we get the optimal solution (least value among all the 50 population) to be 10⁻⁶. For a robust optimization algorithm, it should try to bring most of the population to the near-optimal value (in this case, 10⁻⁶). So, taking 10⁻⁵ as a tolerance value, this work assumes that all the population which are close to a near-optimal value within 10⁻⁵ tolerance to be converged (i.e. absolute difference between the best population - other population < 10⁻⁵).

3.2.2 Scenario 2

A contractor generally aims to obtain an economical mix proportion for a desired compressive strength. It is always a tedious task to find least-cost mix proportions. So, the objective function is to minimize the cost and an additional constraint for desired compressive strength is added to the constraints mentioned above. The cost for each material is obtained from a local material supplier and is presented in Table 3. The cost of superplasticizer is not included in the study as it varies extensively and depends on the supplier. So, the obtained cost is not the final cost of the mix but is a representation of the cost.

Objective Function:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Cost} = & 8 * \text{Cement} + 0.75 * \text{FlyAsh} + 3.5 * \text{GGBS} + 0.85 \\ & * \text{Coarse Aggregate} + 3.5 * \text{Fine Aggregate} \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

Constraints:

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{Predicted Compressive strength from ML model} \\ & > \text{desired compressive strength} \end{aligned}$$

The mix proportions should follow EFNARC and NRMCC guidelines (Association NRMCC 2008)

$$380 < \text{Cement} + \text{Flyash} + \text{Ground Grannular Blastfurnace Slag} < 600$$

$$150 < \text{Water} < 210$$

$$750 < \text{Coarse Aggregate} < 1000$$

$$0.48 * \text{Total Aggregate} < \text{Fine Aggregate} < 0.55 * \text{Total Aggregate}$$

All the constraints and objective function are defined by the mass of material for making 1 m³ of concrete.

Table 3 Materials' Cost

Material (kg/m ³)	Rupees/kg	Kg-e CO ₂ / kg
Cement	8	0.913
Flash	0.75	0.004
GGBS	3.5	0.067
Coarse Aggregate	0.85	0.005
Fine Aggregate	3.5	0.005
Water	-	0.001
Superplasticizer	-	0.01

Table 4 Comparison of the Algorithms' Mechanism used

NCS	DE	NBCS	DCS-1	DCS-2
<p>1. Initialise 'n' nests in the search space for $i=1:n$ $nest(i,:) = lb + \{(ub - lb) * rand(1, nv)\}$ $lb = \text{lower bound}$ $ub = \text{upper bound}$ $nv = \text{number of variables}$ $rand = \text{random number in } [0,1]$</p> <p>2. Generation of new nests $r1 = randperm(n, cuckoo)$ {Selection} for $i=1:cuckoo$ $nest1 = nest(r1(i),:) + levy$ Mantegna's Algorithm for generation of random step sizes $U = N(0, \sigma^2)$ $V = N(0, 1)$ $\sigma^2 = \left\{ \frac{\Gamma(1 + \beta) \sin(\pi\beta/2)}{\beta \Gamma\left(\frac{1 + \beta}{2}\right) \times 2^{\frac{\beta-1}{2}}} \right\}$ $step = \frac{u}{ v ^{\frac{1}{\beta}}}$ $s = \alpha \times step$ $\times \{nest(j,:) - nest(m,:)\}$ $j, m \in [1, 2, \dots, n]$ $levy = randn \times s$ If nest1 has a better fitness than the original nest, update the nest.</p> <p>3. Elimination $k = rand(size(nest)) \leq p$ $step = rand \times k \times \{nest(j,:) - nest(m,:)\}$ for $i=1:n$ $nest1 = nest(i,:) + step$ If nest1 has a better fitness than the original nest, update the nest.</p> <p>4. Repeat step 2 and 3 until termination criteria are satisfied.</p>	<p>1. Initialise 'n' population in the search space for $i=1:n$ $pop(i,:) = lb + \{(ub - lb) * rand(1, nv)\}$ $lb = \text{lower bound}$ $ub = \text{upper bound}$ $nv = \text{number of variables}$ $rand = \text{random number in } [0,1]$</p> <p>2. Generation of New population For $i = 1:n$ Mutation $m(i,:)$ $= pop(i,:) + F * (pop(m,:) - pop(j,:))$ Cross over For $k = 1:nd$ If $r1 < Cr$ $npop(i, k) = m(i, k)$ else $npop(i, k) = pop(i, k)$ end end Selection If npop has better fitness than pop update pop with npop.</p> <p>3. Repeat step 2 until termination condition</p>	<p>1. Initialise 'n' nests in the search space for $i=1:n$ $nest(i,:) = lb + \{(ub - lb) * rand(1, nv)\}$ $lb = \text{lower bound}$ $ub = \text{upper bound}$ $nv = \text{number of variables}$ $rand = \text{random number in } [0,1]$</p> <p>2. Generation of new nests For $i = 1:n$ $nest1 = nest(i,:) + levy$ Mantegna's Algorithm for generation of random step sizes $U = N(0, \sigma^2)$ $V = N(0, 1)$ $\sigma^2 = \left\{ \frac{\Gamma(1 + \beta) \sin(\pi\beta/2)}{\beta \Gamma\left(\frac{1 + \beta}{2}\right) \times 2^{\frac{\beta-1}{2}}} \right\}$ $step = \frac{u}{ v ^{\frac{1}{\beta}}}$ $s = \alpha \times step \times \{nest(i,:) - bestnest\}$ $levy = randn \times s$ If nest1 has a better fitness than the original nest, update the nest.</p> <p>3. Elimination $k = rand(size(nest)) \leq p$ $step = rand \times k \times \{nest(j,:) - nest(m,:)\}$ for $i=1:n$ $nest1 = nest(i,:) + step$ If nest1 has a better fitness than the original nest, update the nest.</p> <p>4. Repeat step 2 and 3 until termination criteria is satisfied.</p>	<p>1. Initialise 'n' nests in the search space for $i=1:n$ $nest(i,:) = lb + \{(ub - lb) * rand(1, nv)\}$ $lb = \text{lower bound}$ $ub = \text{upper bound}$ $nv = \text{number of variables}$ $rand = \text{random number in } [0,1]$</p> <p>2. Generation of new nests For $i = 1:n$ $nest1 = nest(i,:) + levy + DE$ Mantegna's Algorithm for generation of random step sizes $U = N(0, \sigma^2)$ $V = N(0, 1)$ $\sigma^2 = \left\{ \frac{\Gamma(1 + \beta) \sin(\pi\beta/2)}{\beta \Gamma\left(\frac{1 + \beta}{2}\right) \times 2^{\frac{\beta-1}{2}}} \right\}$ $step = \frac{u}{ v ^{\frac{1}{\beta}}}$ $s = \alpha \times step \times \{nest(j,:) - bestnest\}$ $levy = randn \times s$ $DE = 0.9 \times \{nest(k,:) - nest(l,:)\}$ $j, m, k, l \in [1, 2, 3, \dots, n]$ If nest1 has a better fitness than the original nest, update the nest.</p> <p>3. Elimination $k = rand(size(nest)) \leq p$ $step = rand \times k \times \{nest(j,:) - nest(m,:)\}$ for $i=1:n$ $nest1 = nest(i,:) + step$ If nest1 has a better fitness than the original nest, update the nest.</p> <p>4. Repeat step 2 and 3 until termination criteria is satisfied.</p>	<p>1. Initialise 'n' nests in the search space for $i=1:n$ $nest(i,:) = lb + \{(ub - lb) * rand(1, nv)\}$ $lb = \text{lower bound}$ $ub = \text{upper bound}$ $nv = \text{number of variables}$ $rand = \text{random number in } [0,1]$</p> <p>2. Generation of new nests For $i = 1:n$ $nest1 = nest(i,:) + levy + DE$ Mantegna's Algorithm for generation of random step sizes $U = N(0, \sigma^2)$ $V = N(0, 1)$ $\sigma^2 = \left\{ \frac{\Gamma(1 + \beta) \sin(\pi\beta/2)}{\beta \Gamma\left(\frac{1 + \beta}{2}\right) \times 2^{\frac{\beta-1}{2}}} \right\}$ $step = \frac{u}{ v ^{\frac{1}{\beta}}}$ $s = \alpha \times step \times \{nest(i,:) - bestnest\}$ $levy = randn \times s$ $DE = 0.9 \times \{nest(k,:) - nest(l,:)\}$ $j, m, k, l \in [1, 2, 3, \dots, n]$ If nest1 has a better fitness than the original nest, update the nest.</p> <p>3. Elimination $k = rand(size(nest)) \leq p$ $step = rand \times k \times \{nest(j,:) - nest(m,:)\}$ for $i=1:n$ $nest1 = nest(i,:) + step$ If nest1 has a better fitness than the original nest, update the nest.</p> <p>4. Repeat step 2 and 3 until termination criteria is satisfied.</p>

** NCS- Normal Cuckoo Search, NBCS – Normal Best Cuckoo Search, DE – Differential Evolution, DCS-1 – Differential Cuckoo Search type 1, DCS-2 – Differential Cuckoo Search Type-2.

3.2.3 Scenario 3

With an increase on awareness of environmental degradation and the role of human beings in that, research has moved towards eco-friendly concrete. Every manufactured material is associated with a carbon index, i.e. the amount of carbon dioxide released in its manufacturing process. To obtain a good eco-friendly mix, the Carbon-Index of the concrete needs to be reduced. The carbon index associated with each material as shown in Table 3 is taken from United Kingdom Fact Sheet (M. P. Association, 2015) and few research papers (Siddique et al., 2011; Turner & Collins, 2013; Purnell & Black, 2012) Similar to cost optimization, a desired compressive strength will be a constraint along with EFNARC guidelines (EFNARC 1999; EFNARC 2002; Group, 2005).

Objective Function:

$$\begin{aligned} CO_2 \text{ emissions} & \qquad \qquad \qquad (17) \\ & = 0.913 * \text{Cement} + 0.004 * \text{FlyAsh} + 0.067 * \text{GGBS} \\ & + 0.005 * \text{Coarse Aggregate} + 0.005 * \text{Fine Aggregate} \\ & + 0.01 * \text{Superplasticiser} + 0.001 * \text{Water} \end{aligned}$$

Constraints:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Predicted Compressive strength from ANN} \\ & > \text{desired compressive strength} \end{aligned}$$

The mix proportions should follow guidelines of EFNARC and Mineral Products Association (Association, Mineral Products. 2015; Group, 2005).

$$380 < \text{Cement} + \text{Flyash} + \text{Ground Grannular Blastfurnace Slag} < 600$$

$$150 < \text{Water} < 210$$

$$750 < \text{Coarse Aggregate} < 1000$$

$$0.48 * \text{Total Aggregate} < \text{Fine Aggregate} < 0.55 * \text{Total Aggregate}$$

All the constraints and objective function are defined by the mass of material for making 1 m³ of concrete

The single objective optimization is done for all the three scenarios by using the robust optimization technique obtained from the comparison done in stage 1. The constraints are included in the

optimization algorithm using exterior penalty approach. The results obtained are summarized in section 4.

4 Results and Discussion

4.1 Evaluation of robust optimization algorithm

Cuckoo Search, Differential Evolution and the three modifications proposed above are compared for their efficiency using eleven optimization test functions. The comparative analysis is done by two criteria (i) Function Value (ii) Percentage of convergence. After running the algorithm for 100 runs for each objective function the best, the worst and the standard deviation of the function values are shown in the Table 7. The percentage conversion is also performed for every run and the results are depicted for the same. This is calculated by finding a number of nests having fitness value less than the desired number, for example, if the global optimum is 0 then all the nests having fitness values less than 10^{-5} are considered as converged nests.

$$convergence = \frac{\text{total nests having fitness less than a desired value}}{\text{total number of nests taken}} * 100 \quad (18)$$

An optimization algorithm is considered to be best if it can produce the least fitness value, can produce it more frequently or in other words, independent of the initial nest values. As we can see from Table 7, when the CS is enhanced with DE (Differential Cuckoo Search), the functionality of the algorithm is better compared to individual/parent algorithms. The obtained best optimization algorithm “Differential Cuckoo Search - 1” is selected to solve for the Mix design optimization problem.

From the box plots, the deviations between the various algorithms can be observed. Mean, median, standard deviation, outlier limits and various other central tendencies of the distribution can be observed. Moreover, to estimate the statistical significance of the differences more effectively, we have used paired t-test. In our application, all test-functions (f_1 to f_{11}) are minimization functions. The $t.test()$

function in R package is used for estimating the statistical significance of the results. The alternative option-string (alt) is set to "*less*"; R checks whether the difference in mean of the values contained in the vector 1 is less of the mean of the values contained in the vector 2. The baseline groups (vector 2), variable groups (vector 1), their corresponding computed t-statistic, and their probability values (p-values) are presented in Table 9. If the p-value is well above 0.05, it leads us to conclude that we can reject the null hypothesis H_0 in favor of the alternative hypothesis H_1 . If p-value is greater than the confidence interval (0.05) then the 2nd sample (baseline group algorithm) is better than the 1st sample (variable group algorithm). From a geometric perspective on the landscapes of the test functions, it can be noticed that the proposed hybrid approaches perform well in smooth landscapes more than rough landscapes with many local minima. From the observations made for the baseline algorithms DCS-1 and DCS-2, the former is better for 29 comparisons and the latter is better for 28 comparisons. Hence, the formulated mathematical model under different scenarios would be optimized using DCS-1.

Table 5 Shapes of Benchmark Test Functions

f_1 Ackley Function

f_2 Beale Function

f_3 Booth Function

f_4 Matyas Function

f_5 McCormick Function

f_6 Egg Holder Function

f_7 De Jong Function

f_8 Drop-wave Function

f_9 Rosenbrock Function

f_{10} Shubert Function

f_{11} Sphere Function

Table 6 Description of the Benchmark Test Functions

		Description	Input Domain	Optimal Solution
f_1	Ackley Function	$f(\mathbf{x}) = -a \exp \left(-b \sqrt{\frac{1}{d} \sum_{i=1}^d x_i^2} \right) - \exp \left(\frac{1}{d} \sum_{i=1}^d \cos(cx_i) \right) + a + \exp(1)$	$x_i \in [-32.76, 32.76]$, for all $i = 1, \dots, d$. Dimensions (d) = 16. Parameters: $a = 20$, $b = 0.2$ $c = 2\pi$	$f(x^*) = 0$ at $x^* = (0, 0)$
f_2	Beale Function	$f(\mathbf{x}) = (1.5 - x_1 + x_1x_2)^2 + (2.25 - x_1 + x_1x_2^2)^2 + (2.625 - x_1 + x_1x_2^3)^2$	$x_i \in [-4.5, 4.5]$, for all $i = 1, \dots, d$. Dimensions (d) = 2.	$f(x^*) = 0$ at $x^* = (3, 0.5)$
f_3	Booth Function	$f(\mathbf{x}) = (x_1 + 2x_2 - 7)^2 + (2x_1 + x_2 - 5)^2$	$x_i \in [-10, 10]$, for all $i = 1, \dots, d$. Dimensions (d) = 2.	$f(x^*) = 0$ at $x^* = (1, 3)$
f_4	Matyas Function	$f(\mathbf{x}) = 0.26(x_1^2 + x_2^2) - 0.48x_1x_2$	$x_i \in [-10, 10]$, for all $i = 1, \dots, d$. Dimensions (d) = 2.	$f(x^*) = 0$ at $x^* = (0, 0)$
f_5	McCormick Function	$f(\mathbf{x}) = \sin(x_1 + x_2) + (x_1 - x_2)^2 - 1.5x_1 + 2.5x_2 + 1$	$x_1 \in [-1.5, 4]$, $x_2 \in [-3, 4]$ for all $i = 1, \dots, d$. Dimensions (d) = 2.	$f(x^*) = -1.9133$ at $x^* = (-0.541, -1.547)$
f_6	Egg Holder Function	$f(\mathbf{x}^*) = -959.6407, \text{ at } \mathbf{x}^* = (512, 404.2319)$	$x_i \in [-512, 512]$, for all $i = 1, 2$.	$f(x^*) = -959.6407$ $x^* = (512, 404.2319)$

f_7	De Jong Function	$f(\mathbf{x}) = \left(0.002 + \sum_{i=1}^{25} \frac{1}{i + (x_1 - a_{1i})^6 + (x_2 - a_{2i})^6} \right)^{-1}, \text{ where}$ $\mathbf{a} = \begin{pmatrix} -32 & -16 & 0 & 16 & 32 & -32 & \dots & 0 & 16 & 32 \\ -32 & -32 & -32 & -32 & -32 & -16 & \dots & 32 & 32 & 32 \end{pmatrix}$	$x_i \in [-65.536, 65.536],$ for all $i = 1, 2.$	$f(x^*) = 0$ $x^* = (0, \dots, 0)$
f_8	Drop-wave Function	$f(\mathbf{x}) = -\frac{1 + \cos\left(12\sqrt{x_1^2 + x_2^2}\right)}{0.5(x_1^2 + x_2^2) + 2}$	$x_i \in [-5.12, 5.12],$ for all $i = 1, 2.$	$f(x^*) = -1$ $x^* = (0, 0)$
f_9	Rosenbrock Function	$f(\mathbf{x}) = \sum_{i=1}^{d-1} [100(x_{i+1} - x_i^2)^2 + (x_i - 1)^2]$	$x_i \in [-5, 10],$ for all $i =$ $1, \dots, d$	$f(x^*) = 0$ $x^* = (1, \dots, 1)$
f_{10}	Shubert Function	$f(\mathbf{x}) = \left(\sum_{i=1}^5 i \cos((i+1)x_1 + i) \right) \left(\sum_{i=1}^5 i \cos((i+1)x_2 + i) \right)$	$x_i \in [-10, 10],$ for all $i =$ $1, 2$	$f(x^*) = -186.7309$
f_{11}	Sphere Function	$f(\mathbf{x}) = \sum_{i=1}^d x_i^2$	$x_i \in [-5.12, 5.12],$ for all $i = 1, \dots, d.$	$f(x^*) = 0$ $x^* = (0, \dots, 0)$

Table 7 Comparison between all the algorithms using 11 different test functions

		NCS		DE		NBCS		DCS-1		DCS-2	
		Function	Convergence	Function	Convergence	Function	Convergence	Function	Convergence	Function	Convergence
f_1	min	1.46636E-06	04.000	2.85799635	100	6.58483E-07	36.000	7.55351E-11	100	6.10436E-11	100
	std	0.000425426	23.842	0.73464445	0	3.14384E-06	09.730	1.36451E-09	0	1.81492E-09	0
	max	0.003412398	100	7.26860074	100	1.96842E-05	100	1.1165E-08	100	1.40554E-08	100
f_2	min	6.29442E-11	04.000	6.0318E-11	100	8.61245E-09	04.000	4.48104E-15	12.000	9.51963E-15	14.000
	std	1.31537E-05	08.523	0.6475981	0	0.000134179	02.955	6.21601E-07	14.371	5.52069E-08	08.920
	max	7.09565E-05	44.000	3.48245313	100	0.000770731	20.000	6.2275E-06	100	5.15419E-07	100
f_3	min	3.44993E-11	08.000	5.8207E-12	100	7.02148E-10	04.000	8.16648E-18	96.000	5.38752E-17	96.000
	std	7.67798E-07	11.306	3.41810635	0	1.90967E-06	10.879	1.27297E-12	01.020	1.96689E-12	0.6823
	max	4.97372E-06	68.000	24.9687148	100	1.10263E-05	64.000	1.11429E-11	100	1.34883E-11	100
f_4	min	1.28693E-11	48.000	1.4902E-18	100	1.42394E-11	40.000	1.0667E-17	96.000	9.83559E-19	96.000
	std	2.23242E-08	09.886	0.0707281	0	7.77554E-08	10.073	3.76918E-14	0.6823	8.78123E-14	0.6823
	max	1.46699E-07	92.000	0.36648093	100	5.072E-07	92.000	2.81028E-13	100	7.24297E-13	100
f_5	min	-1.913222955	28.000	-1.913223	100	-1.913222954	20.000	-1.913222955	92.000	-1.913222955	96.000
	std	2.03998E-07	10.812	0.207510	0	3.52048E-07	12.236	9.06913E-12	01.459	3.14652E-13	01.345
	max	-1.913220986	80.000	-1.022469	100	-1.913220276	72.000	-1.913222955	100	-1.913222955	100
f_6	Min	-959.641	02.000	-959.64066	100	-959.641000	24.000	-959.641	70.000	-959.641	70.000
	Std	1.319238	01.7192	17.180812	0	1.85E-13	08.768	0.00000	04.645	0.00000	04.416
	max	-946.467	06.000	-858.60121	100	-959.641000	78.000	-959.641	94.000	-959.641	96.000
f_7	Min	0.998004	02.000	0.998004	100	0.99800400	84.000	0.998004	92.000	0.998004	92.000
	Std	4.45E-10	05.993	0.546043	0	1.12E-16	2.4790	1.12E-16	01.831	1.12E-16	01.827
	max	0.998004	30.000	5.928845	100	0.99800400	100	0.998004	100	0.998004	100
f_8	Min	-1.00000	00.000	-1.00000	100	-1.00000	42.000	-1.00000	76.000	-1.00000	72.000
	Std	0.007631	02.334	0.00000	0	3.42E-13	07.556	0.00000	04.566	0.00000	04.571
	max	-0.93625	16.000	-1.00000	100	-1.00000	76.000	-1.00000	98.000	-1.00000	98.000

f_9	Min	3.49E-29	78.000	2.766649	100	5.85E-07	0	8.59E-16	96.000	7.17E-16	96.000
	Std	1.67E-17	03.562	0.933633	0	0.006154	02.324	2.59E-10	01.011	3.37E-11	01.088
	max	1.28E-16	96.000	8.292449	100	0.039016	12.000	2.13E-09	100	3.02E-10	100
f_{10}	Min	-186.731	0.0000	-186.730909	100	-186.731	76.000	-186.731	44.000	-186.731	46.000
	Std	0.000443	0.2814	9.6298E-15	0	4.91E-11	4.33034	4.65E-09	07.965	9.18E-09	07.581
	max	-186.729	2.0000	-186.730909	100	-186.731	98.000	-186.731	82.000	-186.731	82.000
f_{11}	Min	4.89E-17	100	5.3964E-133	100	2.17E-33	100	8.65E-137	100	1.25E-210	100
	Std	1.95E-16	0	3.3056E-129	0	2.29E-31	0	5.22E-135	0	6.78E-156	0
	max	1.18E-15	100	2.5035E-128	100	2.17E-30	100	3.97E-134	100	6.65E-155	100

Table 8 Box Plot of the Performance of the Algorithms

f_7 De Jong Function

f_8 Drop-wave Function

f_9 Rosenbrock Function

f_{10} Shubert Function

f_{11} Sphere Function

Table 9 Statistical tests for Algorithms

		Baseline group		DCS1	DCS2	
f_1	Ackley Function	Variable Groups	t-Stat	p-value	t-Stat	p-value
		NCS	3.5362	0.9997	3.7078	0.9998
		NBCS	13.936	1.0000	13.877	1.0000
		DE	61.793	1.0000	62.086	1.0000
		DCS (1/2)*	0.9903	0.8378	-0.9903	0.1622
f_2	Beale Function	NCS	-9.0147	7.7E-15	-8.4047	1.6E-13
		NBCS	-6.1696	7.5E-09	-4.8241	2.5E-06
		DE	-7.3987	2.2E-11	-5.3493	2.8E-07
		DCS(1/2)	-2.5228	0.0066	2.5228	0.0491
f_3	Booth Function	NCS	4.8190	1.0000	4.8190	1.0000
		NBCS	6.8559	1.0000	6.8559	1.0000
		DE	3.9889	0.9999	3.9889	0.9999
		DCS(1/2)	0.6376	0.7374	-0.6376	0.2626
f_4	Matyas Function	NCS	5.8003	1.0000	5.8003	1.0000
		NBCS	6.1458	1.0000	6.1458	1.0000
		DE	4.4845	1.0000	4.4845	1.0000
		DCS(1/2)	0.9750	0.8340	-0.9750	0.1660
f_5	McCormick Function	NCS	1.8937	0.9694	1.8937	0.9694
		NBCS	4.6675	1.0000	4.6675	1.0000
		DE	4.8938	1.0000	4.8938	1.0000
		DCS(1/2)	-1.0137	0.1566	1.0137	0.8434
f_6	Egg Holder Function	NCS	1.0955	0.8620	1.0955	0.8620
		NBCS	1.0000	0.8401	1.0000	0.8401
		DE	2.2445	0.0065	2.2445	0.0065
		DCS(1/2)	NaN	NA	NaN	NaN
f_7	De Jong Function	NCS	4.1883	1.0000	4.1883	1.0000
		NBCS	0.2569	0.6011	0.83076	0.7959
		DE	2.9341	0.9979	2.9341	0.9979
		DCS(1/2)	-0.5637	0.2871	0.56375	0.7129
f_8	Drop-wave Function	NCS	1.6592	0.9499	1.6592	0.9499
		NBCS	2.6130	0.9948	2.6130	0.9948
		DE	1.4214	0.0208	1.4214	0.0208
		DCS(1/2)	NaN	NA	NaN	NaN
f_9	Rosenbrock Function	NCS	-1.5053	0.0677	-1.9718	0.0257
		NBCS	3.0451	0.9985	3.0451	0.9985
		DE	61.911	1.0000	61.911	1.0000
		DCS(1/2)	-1.2343	0.1100	1.2343	0.8900
f_{10}	Shubert Function	NCS	8.5560	1.0000	8.5560	1.0000
		NBCS	-7.3299	3.1E-11	-5.3142	3.3E-07
		DE	-7.3987	2.2E-11	-5.3493	2.8E-07
		DCS(1/2)	1.3932	0.9167	-1.3932	0.0833
f_{11}	Sphere Function	NCS	14.036	1.0000	14.036	1.0000
		NBCS	3.5522	0.9997	3.5535	0.9997
		DE	-5.8285	3.5E-08	3.9459	3.5E-08
		DCS(1/2)	-5.8285	3.5E-08	5.8285	1.0000

* DCS (1/2): If Baseline group is DCS1, then variable group is DCS 2.

4.2 Performance metrics of machine learning models

The five statistical parameters (also known as performance metrics) to evaluate the efficiency of ML techniques used in the present study are R, R^2 , RMSE, MAE and MAPE; they are summarized in Table 10. Only a limited variation in these metrics is observed on performing multiple iterations.

Table 10 Performance evaluation of ML models

ML Model	R	R^2	RMSE	MAE	MAPE
ANN	0.919	0.845	5.697	4.191	12.866
SVR	0.923	0.852	5.608	3.904	11.137

It is observed from Table 10 that SVR performs better than ANN in terms of correlation (R & R^2) and error (RMSE). However, the variations in the performance metrics for SVR and ANN is not very significant and both these ML techniques may be used for testing the available data to obtain the knowledge model. The developed knowledge model from both the ML approaches are used for obtaining the optimal mix proportion using DCS-1 under three different scenarios. Table 11, 12 and 13 shows the results of optimal mix proportion obtained using DCS-1 for Scenario 1, 2 and 3 respectively.

Table 11 Scenario 1: Optimal Mix Proportion for obtaining Maximum Compressive Strength

Material (kg/m^3)	SVR	ANN
C	490.00	490.30
GGBS	110.00	0.14
FLYA	0.00	109.49
CA	900.00	870.29
FA	830.77	1022.67
W	158.54	155.25
Compressive Strength (MPa)	69.14	98.75

It is observed from Table 11 that ANN achieved a 30% increased compressive strength in comparison with SVR based framework. The compressive strength obtained are 98.75 MPa using ANN and 69.14 MPa using SVR. The weight of GGBS was very low (0.14 kg/m³) using ANN but SVR's mix design had 110 kg/m³. Similarly, the weight of fly ash using ANN was 109.49 kg/m³ but it was nil for the mix proportion using SVR. From Table 12, it is observed that the variation of the cost of the economical mix for a fixed compressive strength (30 MPa and 50 MPa) is relatively low in the range of 2 to 4 % only while solving using SVR and ANN approaches. The water content in the ANN approach in both the cases used is around 36% more in comparison with SVR mix proportion. While optimizing for cost, the mix proportions obtained by ANN and SVR eliminated the use of GGBS and fly ash in both the cases of compressive strength i.e., 30 MPa and 50 MPa.

Table 12 Scenario 2: Obtaining Economical Mix for desirable compressive strength

Material (kg/m ³)	CS (Expected) = 30		CS (Expected) = 50	
	SVR	ANN	SVR	ANN
Cost (Rs./m ³)	6100.93	6395.33	6769.21	6626.52
C	380.00	416.79	380.24	441.39
GGBS	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
FLYA	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
CA	750.06	750.03	799.82	751.58
FA	692.38	692.42	870.70	701.89
W	152.21	207.42	150.01	209.38

Table 13 Scenario 3: Obtaining Eco-friendly Mix for desirable compressive strength

Material (kg/m ³)	CS (Expected) = 30		CS (Expected) =50	
	SVR	ANN	SVR	ANN
Embodied Carbon (Kg-e CO ₂ /m ³)	354.31	378.95	428.97	405.77
C	380.01	406.13	460.08	433.58
GGBS	0.00	0.00	15.12	25.11
FLYA	0.00	0.00	1.43	0.00
CA	750.03	752.15	769.89	790.51
FA	692.56	847.98	722.36	825.46
W	150.03	154.77	150.01	150.02

The results of mix proportions obtained in Scenario 3 as shown in Table 13 for embodied carbon also didn't show too much variation while solving using ANN and SVR. SVR achieved a lower embodied carbon for compressive strength of 30 MPa and ANN achieved the least embodied carbon for compressive strength of 50 MPa. In all these mix proportions it was observed that the weights of GGBS and fly ash are zero for compressive strength of 30 MPa and relatively low for compressive strength of 50 MPa. It can be inferred from all the three scenarios that for obtaining a mix proportion to achieve maximum compressive strength, ANN-based bio-inspired optimization model works better and for minimization of cost as well as minimization of embodied carbon scenarios, both the models were able to produce optimal mix proportions with a very small variation. The optimized SCC mix proportions of ingredients in all the three cases are encouraging and can be suitably used for reducing the number of trial mixtures to achieve the desired properties of SCC in the field.

5 Conclusion

This work focusses on using machine learning models and bio-inspired optimization algorithms to obtain mix proportions for desired compressive strengths. Two machine learning algorithms are successfully modelled and are compared to prove their efficiency. The comparative analysis based on experimental verification shows that both models can predict the compressive strengths of concrete accurately. Two bio-inspired hybrid optimization algorithms have been tested with their parent algorithms and are proved to be working better in terms of both faster convergence and robustness. The obtained trained models are used to predict mix proportions in three different scenarios: (i) Maximization of compressive strength, (ii) Minimization of cost and (iii) Minimization of embodied carbon. As SVR cannot be used for extrapolation, it was not able to produce a mix proportion which has a compressive strength more than the maximum compressive strength mix present in the data set taken. Based on the results, it is concluded that for obtaining a mix proportion which has a maximum compressive strength, ANN-based bio-

inspired optimization model works better. In minimization of cost and minimization of embodied carbon scenarios, both the models were able to produce optimal SCC mix proportions. The optimized proportions of ingredients in all the three cases are encouraging and validate very well with the results. The outcome of this work is useful in reducing the number of trial mixtures to achieve the desired properties of SCC in the field. Further, this work may be extended by applying more number of supervised machine learning approaches which could come up with even better mix designs that are a hybrid of one or more techniques.

Conflict of Interest

On behalf of all authors, the corresponding author states that there is no conflict of interest.

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